

HISTORY OF PRESS BODIES AT THE BEGINNING OF THE 20th CENTURY

Tillayev D.O.

Academic lyceum at UrDU, senior history teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14017483>

Abstract. *This article provides detailed information about the history of the press and the activities of the Jadids. It is noted that various newspapers were published in order to promote the cultural and educational ideas, which promoted the national idea. People who contributed to the formation of the press are also mentioned.*

Keywords: *press, national idea, newspaper, modern, Turkestan, ideology, nation.*

INTRODUCTION

By the 21st century, which is the age of globalization, many innovations are introduced into modern literature. These innovations, on the one hand, are a natural development and a contribution to the development of national literature, and on the other hand, they are changes under the influence of Europe and the world. At the same time, literature and history play an important role in informing the society. The contribution of Turkestan thinkers to the development of science, the socio-political life of Muslim countries in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, the emergence of the Jadid movement, the role of Jadid representatives in this movement and the press activities are being studied in scientific research centers of the world. Since the beginning of mankind, there has been a need for mutual information exchange. Initially, the process of information exchange between people was carried out through oral speech, and later, with the appearance of writing, a great leap occurred in the process of information dissemination. With the printing of books, the process of information exchange became stronger. In general, with the development of humanity, the exchange of information also accelerates. On the one hand, with the progress of humanity, information is increasing, and as a result of new technical discoveries, complex forms of its transmission and memory appear. On the other hand, as the volume of information increases, the need for new communication sources begins to be felt.

Our wise people say that the past and the future are one step at a time. The history of the press has its unfading stars, shining suns - great figures. After all, like the dawn after night, they sympathize with the pain of generations and help them on their way with their free-thinking powers. The pioneers who put forward the problems of the new school and education, upbringing and training are such great people, and they have a special place in the field of history. The ideas promoted by the Jadids have not lost their importance. Thoughts transparent like a pearl sunk in the bottom of the water, advanced philosophical and pedagogical views are very necessary and significant in raising a mature generation today. In particular, the importance of the activities of the youth in educating young people as the possessor of a beautiful mind, a beautiful language, a beautiful heart - a perfect human being is great and incomparable.

In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, Jadids were widely active in Turkestan region in order to fight for national independence, establish democratic rules, and save the people from ignorance and superstition. They correctly understood that the press is a powerful force in achieving such a good goal. In this direction, well-known representatives of the jadid movement in Turkestan region such as Makhmudkhoja Bekhbudi, Faizulla Khojayeov, Abdurauf Fitrat,

Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov, Abdulla Avloni, Ubaidulla Khojayev played an important role in the formation of the local press. The establishment of national periodicals in the region was facilitated by the newspaper "Tarjumon" published by Ismailbey Gaspirali (Gaspirinsky) (1851-1914) in 1883-1918, a representative of the Crimean Tatar nation, and "Sirotul Mustaqim" ("To'ghri Yol"), the influence of newspapers such as "Sirojul Akhbar Afganiya" ("Illuminator of Afghan News"), published in Afghanistan in 1900-1919, was great. In addition, press organizations published in India and Egypt also entered Bukhara at the beginning of the 20th century. In particular, magazines such as "Habl-ul-matn" published in Persian language from India and "Chehranoma" from Egypt came. Research and studies have shown that "Al-jadid" newspaper from Iran also came to Bukhara. Through the above-mentioned newspapers and magazines, intellectuals of Bukhara are informed about world events, military actions in the fields of World War I, world economy, science and technology, and they are convinced that the country they live in is behind the development they did. Sadridin Ainiy (1878-1954), one of the representatives of Jadids who opposed the monarchy system in Bukhara, notes that he understood the essence of the word "parliament" after reading the "Tarjumon" newspaper. The publication of Taraqqi newspaper in 1906 under the editorship of Ismail Obidov played an important role in the emergence of a truly local press in Turkestan at the beginning of the 20th century. Despite the strict censorship of the local authorities of the Russian Empire, such press bodies as "Khurshid" (1906), "Shuhrat" (1907), "Asiyo" (1908) were published. Since this newspaper was the first press organ, June 27, when it was published, is celebrated as "press day" in Uzbekistan. The second stage of the development of the national press covers the years 1912-1915. During this period, press organizations such as "Samarkand", "Oyina" (1913), "Sadoi Turkistan" (1914-1915), "Sadoi Fergana" (1914) despite serious obstacles and problems in their way, played an important role in the formation of national consciousness, national language, national literature and journalism. In 1917, when the historical processes took a sharp turn, when the February revolution and the October coup took place, dozens of newspapers and magazines promoting social and political activity and ensuring national unity were active. Newspapers "Najot", "Turk Eli", "Turon", "Ulug' Turkistan", "Khurriyat", "El Bayroghi", "Yurt", "Chayon" magazines published in this year can be noted. At the beginning of the 20th century, a progressive movement arose in the Emirate of Bukhara, a semi-colony of the Russian Empire. This was manifested in the process of opening schools of the new method and in the structure of the secret society "Tarbiyyi atfol" ("Children's education"). Abduvahid Burhanov (Munzim), Ahmadjon Hamdiy, Mukamil Burhanov, Hamidkhoja Mehriy, and Khoja Rafi were leaders and initiators in the creation of "Tarbiyyai atfol". Later, the ranks of this society expanded, and practical measures were taken to end illiteracy in the emirate through newspapers, magazines, and educational books. Members of the "Children's Education" society, using their financial resources, through the organizations "Book Trade Friendship Education Society" and the "Blessing Shareholder Society", sell religious and secular literature published in cities such as Baku (Azerbaijan), Istanbul (Turkey) and they began to secretly distribute newspapers and magazines among the people. The influence of the political agency of the Russian Empire in Bukhara (1885-1917), established in 1885, increased in the political life of the Bukhara Emirate. Official permission from this office of the Russian government was required to publish newspapers and various other books in the country.

Jadidism is a national progressive movement of Turkestan intellectuals of the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century aimed at wide promotion and implementation

of the ideas of freedom, democracy, culture and education among the people. It is known that "Our ancestors regularly dealt with political issues - rights, national state, and power". At the same time, the reform of school education began. A national press was launched. A theater appeared. A new literature was formed, in a word, a new way of thinking appeared. It was the ideology of national identity and independence. This situation was, without a doubt, unprecedented in the historical development of the nation over the next 3-4 centuries. It was a sign of the beginning of a new phase in its life after a long period of stagnation. In this sense, we can say that the modern press is not a one-sided ideological press of the Soviet era, it was a press that led the nation to struggle and enlightenment. The restoration of the truth about the press of Jadids is directly connected with the realization of national independence. The emergence of Jadid press plays an important role in the spread of national ideas in the country.

It is difficult to separate the concepts of national idea and national ideology, they are intertwined. The concept of national ideology is comprehensive, and the national idea is its core. National ideology is formed around the national idea, which covers all areas from the cultural and spiritual aspects of the life of society and the country to political views. National ideology feeds the national idea and strengthens it. They respond to people's understanding of what values they want to protect their country and life in the future, how they imagine it and what they rely on in their struggle. During the period of the Soviet totalitarian regime, the question of which ideas opposed the ideology of Turkestan conquest and what they were based on can be answered based on the ideas of national progressives and independence movements.

In the national idea of the Jadids, the following two issues were set as the main goals: first, to raise our people to the level of enlightened nations of the world; the second is to build a national-democratic state in Turkestan. In their view of the state and society, these two issues are inextricably linked. Because in order for the nation to be enlightened, it must develop in its own way without being subject to others. For this, our people should first of all acquire knowledge. Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Munavvar Qari Abdurashidkhanov, Abdurauf Fitrat, Abdulla Avloni, Abdulla Qadiri, Cholpon are great geniuses as mentioned above. A number of problems in the field of education are reflected in their views on the press. Language and education are one of the characteristics that show the identity of a nation. Without these two, a nation cannot be independent. Abdulla Avloni, who understood this with wisdom, writes: "To lose the national language is to lose the soul of the nation. Hey! We Turkestans are forgetting and losing our national language day by day, let alone preserving it".

The ideas promoted by our progressives have not lost their importance. They well understood the need to enlighten the people, raise their culture, and make the people confident in their own strength and capabilities. Naturally, every nation needs to use world scientific innovations and universal ideas for its development. But with one important condition. These thoughts and ideas should pass through the hearts and minds of the nation, that is, "nationalize". Jadids see in nationality not only the development of the nation, but also the guarantee of survival and even its preservation. Intellectuals, on the one hand, fought for the independence of Turkestan. On the other hand, they sought to build a democratic legal state in Turkestan. This struggle forms the basis of Jadidist ideology. The feeling of boundless love for the motherland - Turkistan, thoughts about its future, drawing up a plan for the development of the homeland, combining Eastern and Western traditions are the important factors that pushed the jadids to this path. The founder of the national movement in Turkestan, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, wrote in the magazine

"Oyina" the following: "People who do not know the name of their tribe and the names of their seven fathers are called 'slave-marquq'".

In the works of Behbudi, Fitrat, Cholpon, Munavvarqori and other progressive intellectuals, we can see that the main link of the national idea - the idea of uniting all local peoples in Turkestan - was a red thread. Behbudi showed this situation as follows: "If we Muslims of Turkestan want to unite our religion and nation and take steps towards reform and union from today, our intellectuals and progressives, the rich and scholars unite, and serve for the development of religion and nation, Motherland, then we will not be dependent on others". For this, our people should first of all acquire knowledge.

One of the important components of the idea of national progressives was the development of historical consciousness, learning from history. Abdurauf Fitrat wrote about this in 1917: "History is a science that studies the past, development and causes of decline of nations". These advanced intellectuals of Turkestan were actively engaged in the method of administration, forms of government, theory and practice of statehood in Turkestan. Special attention was paid to issues of statehood in the programs of the parties of Young Bukharas, Young Khivalites, "Sho'roi Islamiya", "Shoroi Ulamo", "Turon" and other societies. This not only indicated that Jadidism had moved from enlightenment to politics, but also meant that the struggle to fundamentally change society and achieve independence in our country had begun.

Historical experience shows that our forefathers for centuries considered it a great thing to be faithful to their families, sacred soil, religious beliefs, customs and traditions. Thousands of loyal sons of our nation sacrificed their lives for the preservation of these ancient traditions, and were martyred in the battles for the country's independence. The national-liberation movement, which has not stopped since the occupation of Turkestan by Russia, had a great impact on the people's realization of their national identity, strengthening their patriotic aspirations for the freedom and independence of their homeland and nation. It is well known to us that the Jadids intended to implement their reforms step by step, to achieve progress and development only peacefully through the parliament. They tried to seize power peacefully, taking into account the unique national mentality of Uzbek people, their sincerity, generosity, patience, endurance. This unique national idea in the work of the Jadids later became a phenomenon of world importance, and it was further developed by the leaders of the national-liberation forces in India and other countries. "Rights are taken, not given!" The slogan has become the rallying cry of the nation today. The people of every nation and country won their rights through struggle. However, Behbudi was in favor of fighting for independence without shedding blood. He believed that a lot could be achieved through parliament.

The Turkestan Autonomous Government, which fought for independence and freedom, to establish autonomy in Turkestan through the parliamentary way, was drowned in blood by the Bolsheviks. An authoritarian Soviet regime based on communist ideology was established in Turkestan. However, the national ideology and national idea did not die in our country even during the Soviet era, it continued to live.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the activities of the Tatar enlighteners in the creation and development of the periodical press and printing works in Turkestan have hardly been researched. Newspapers published in Turkestan in cooperation with Tatar intellectuals informed the subscribers about the events happening in the world. The ideas of freeing Turkestan people from

ignorance, reforming schools and madrasas, and enlightening the nation were put forward. Superstition and bigotry were fought against. Articles condemning colonialism and advocating the independence of Turkestan were published. Because of this, many of these newspapers were short-lived.

REFERENCES

1. Ernazarov T. Time press in Turkestan (1870-1924 years). - Tashkent: State publishing house of the Uzbek SSR, 1959. - P. 7.
2. Isoqboyev AA The activities of Tatar-Bashkir enlighteners in the socio-political and cultural life of Turkestan (late XIX-early XX centuries). candidate of historical sciences diss... - Namangan: 2008. - B. 108.
3. Cholpon. Press in Turkestan. "Society and Management", 1998, No. 2, pp. 40-44.
4. Ochilov N. Periodical press // National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. J.12. -T.: O'ZME publishing house. 2006. -B.227.
5. 1917-1918 gg.): Autoref. diss. ... candy. desire science -T., 2001. -S. 20. 4. Rajabov Q. "Education atfol" // National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. J. 8. -T.: UzME publishing house. 2004. -B. 271.
6. Amonov U. Reading the "Bukhara Sharif" newspaper... //Pedagogical skills. 2007. No. 1. -B. 50-51.
7. Chronicle of the history of Uzbekistan / Authors: Rajabov Q, Hasanov F. - T.: National encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2007. -B. 88-89.
8. Ainiy S. Materials for the history of Bukhara revolution / Works. 8 roofs. T.1. -T., 1963. -B. 243.